

gives a 15 proton multiplet at 2.9 τ (aromatic protons), a two proton singlet at 5.2 τ (-CH₂-protons) and a three proton singlet at 7.7 τ (methyl protons). In the mass spectrum, molecular ion peak at m/e 328 constitutes the base peak.

Reaction of α -methylbenzalidenebenzylamine with diphenylketene: To a boiling xylene solution of the imine (0.01 mole) was added diphenylketene generated by the thermal decomposition⁴ of α -diazo- α -phenylacetophenone⁶. The mixture was heated for a while. The solvent was removed *in vacuo* and the residue was recrystallized from benzene petroleum ether, m.p. 156°, yield 65%.

Infrared spectrum of the above adduct indicates absorption bands at 1740 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of β -lactam carbonyl. NMR spectrum shows 20 protons as a multiplet at 2.7 τ (aromatic), a two proton singlet at 5.2 τ (methylene) and a three proton singlet at 7.6 τ (methyl).

In case of hydroxy substituted imine, esterification of phenolic group also took place. Thus the cycloadduct having esterified phenolic group was obtained.

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Interaction of 2-Amino-4-Phenyl-5-Arylazothiazoles with 2-Nitro, 3-Nitro and 4-Nitro Benzaldehydes

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ALTHOUGH various N-aryl-N'-2-thiazolythioureas have been prepared by the interaction of arylisothiocyanates and 2-aminothiazole derivatives, the reaction of benzaldehydes with thiazole derivatives has not been investigated. Moreover, thiazole derivatives are of considerable interest from therapeutic point of view because of their utility as antifungal¹, antibacterial², antitumor³, anthelmintic⁴, local anaesthetic, diuretic⁵ and adrenergic agents. Thiazole derivatives contain thiourea moiety and,

therefore, like urea derivatives can possibly act as hypoglycemic agents⁶. In view of these possibilities, various substituted thiazole derivatives (A) were synthesised to study their biological activities.

The compounds (A) described in this communication have been synthesised by reacting 2-amino-4-phenyl-5-arylazothiazoles⁷ with different nitro derivatives of benzaldehydes. The structure of these compounds have been established on the basis of elemental analysis and ir and mass spectral studies. The reactivity of 2-amino-4-phenyl-5-arylazothiazole was smooth and the product was obtained in good yield. Colour of all these compounds ranges from dark yellow to brown.

Experimental

Preparation of 4-phenyl-5-arylozo-2-(azomethine-4-nitrophenyl) thiazole: 2-Amino-4-phenyl-5-arylazothiazole (0.002 mol) was dissolved in alcohol (25 ml) and a hot solution of 4-nitrobenzaldehyde (0.002 mol) in alcohol (20 ml) was added to it. The contents were refluxed for 3 hrs in presence of 0.2 ml piperidine. On cooling, shining crystals separated out which were recrystallised from 60% ethyl alcohol. All m.p.s are uncorrected. IR spectra were taken in KBr film on a Backmann IR spectrophotometer and mass spectral studies were carried out on a Varian Mat-CH-7 mass spectrophotometer. 2-Amino-4-phenyl-5-arylazothiazoles were prepared by the reported method⁷.

Analysis: m.p. 165°; Found: N, 16.7%. Calcd. for C₂₂H₁₅N₃O₂S; N, 16.94%; $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 1610 cm⁻¹ (-N=N-), 1640 cm⁻¹ (C=C or C=N) 830-690 cm⁻¹ (substituted phenyl); $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{CH}_2\text{OH}}$ at 420 nm for -N=N- grouping and 270 nm for C₆H₅NO₂; M⁺ at m/e 413.

Other 4-phenyl-5-arylozo-2-(azomethine-3-nitrophenyl)/4-phenyl-5-arylozo-2-(azomethine-2-nitrophenyl) thiazoles were prepared in the same way by taking suitably substituted nitrobenzaldehydes. Their characteristics are compiled in Table 1.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS OF 4-PHENYL-5-ARYLAZO-2-(AZOMETHINE-NITROPHENYL) THIAZOLES

Sl. No.		R	m.p. °C	Yield %
1.		H	165	50
2.		2-OH ₃	160	60
3.		3-OH ₃	180	60
4.		4-OH ₃	116	65
5.		2-OCH ₃	148	50
6.		3-OCH ₃	142	50

(Table 1 Contd.)

7.	"	4-OCH ₃	112	60
8.	"	2-OC ₂ H ₅	108	45
9.	"	4-OC ₂ H ₅	140	50
10.	"	3-NO ₂	98	65
11.	"	4-NO ₂	100	70
12.	R=3-NO ₂	H	140	50
13.	"	2-OH ₃	153	60
14.	"	3-CH ₃	137	65
15.	"	4-CH ₃	120	65
16.	"	2-OCH ₃	176	50
17.	"	3-OCH ₃	182	45
18.	"	4-OCH ₃	143	55
19.	R=3-NO ₂	2-OC ₂ H ₅	140	50
20.	"	4-OC ₂ H ₅	123	45
21.	"	3-NO ₂	110	60
22.	"	4-NO ₂	96	65
23.	R=2-NO ₂	H	169	60
24.	"	2-OH ₃	152	55
25.	"	3-OH ₃	147	60
26.	"	4-OH ₃	132	65
27.	"	2-OCH ₃	127	50
28.	"	3-OCH ₃	176-178	50
29.	"	4-OCH ₃	150	45
30.	"	2-OC ₂ H ₅	143	50
31.	"	4-OC ₂ H ₅	160	55
32.	"	3-NO ₂	120	65
33.	"	4-NO ₂	107-109	65

All compounds gave consistent nitrogen analysis.

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Studies on Bromophenols. Part I—Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of 2-Phenyl-2-(2'-Hydroxy-3'-Bromo-5'-Methylphenyl)-3-Aryl-5 H/Methyl/Carboxymethyl-4-Thiazolidinones

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BROMOPHENOLS possess antibacterial¹, antifungal², antiseptic³, germicidal⁴ and other biological activities. 4-Thiazolidinones are also associated with various kinds of biological activities

like hypnotic⁵, anaesthetic⁶, antifungal⁷ etc. With a view to get more active drugs we have prepared 4-thiazolidinones of type (I) containing bromophenol residue by the action of thioglycolic acid, thiolactic acid or thiomalic acid on Schiff bases which were obtained by condensing 2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-methyl benzophenone⁸ with different aromatic amines. The constitution was supported by ir spectra⁹⁻¹¹. The products were screened for antimicrobial activity.

(I)

R = Aryl
R₁ = H, CH₃, OH, COOH

IR spectra: The ir spectra of 4-thiazolidinones of type (I) were taken on KBr pellets and characterised. The >C=O group frequency was obtained at 1640 nm, >N-CO at 1590 nm and phenolic OH at 3410 nm.

Experimental

Preparation of α-phenyl-2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-methylbenzal anil: Aniline (0.1 mole) was added to a solution of 2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-methylbenzophenone (0.1 mole) in dry benzene (25 ml) and refluxed for 6 hrs. The product was isolated and crystallised from ethanol. Yield 75%, m.p. 62°. (Found: C, 65.35; H, 4.50; N, 3.75%. C₂₀H₁₆NOBr requires, C, 65.57; H, 4.37; N, 3.83%). Other anils were prepared similarly (Physical constants are recorded in Table 1).

Preparation of 2-phenyl-2-(2'-hydroxy-3'-bromo-5'-methylphenyl)-3-phenyl-4-thiazolidinone: Thioglycolic acid (0.01 mole) was added to a solution of α-phenyl-2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-methylbenzal anil (0.01 mole) in dry benzene (25 ml) and refluxed for 6 hrs. The product was isolated and crystallised from ethanol. Yield 61%, m.p. 78°. (Found: C, 60.25; H, 4.00; N, 3.25. C₂₂H₁₈NO₂SBr requires C, 60.00; H, 4.09; N, 3.18%). Other anils were treated with thioglycolic acid similarly (Physical constants are recorded in Table 2).

Preparation of 2-phenyl-2-(2'-hydroxy-3'-bromo-5'-methylphenyl)-3-phenyl-5-methyl-4-thiazolidinone: Thiolactic acid (0.01 mole) was added to a solution of α-phenyl-2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-methylbenzal anil (0.01 mole) in dry benzene (25 ml) and refluxed for 6 hrs. The product was isolated and crystallised from ethanol. Yield 67%, m.p. 68°. (Found: C, 60.75; H, 4.50; N, 3.00. C₂₃H₂₀NO₂SBr requires C, 60.53; H, 4.41; N, 3.08%). Other anils were treated with thiolactic acid similarly (Physical constants are recorded in Table 2).

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